

THE ROLE OF EUROPEAN UNION POLICIES ON THE MANAGEMENT OF REFERENCE MATERIALS SPECIFIC TO FOOD ENGINEERING

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Abstract

Purpose – This paper presents the decisive role of the European Commission (EC) policy in the development of reference materials (RM), specific to food engineering.

Methodology/approach - The authors of this paper carried out a documentary study on the dynamics of the EC policy in the field of RM production and the implementation of these policies beyond 2014.

Findings – By analyzing the regulations issued by the European Union we can observe a significant increase in the financing of projects on the development of reference materials used to evaluate the performance of testing the quality of agri-food products.

Research limitations/implications – Since 2014, the fight against food fraud is included into the EC's food safety policy. The policies in the field of food safety have expanded their regulatory area by including provisions regarding food fraud. The authors performed a research on the dynamics of the EC policy in the field of RM production and the implementation of these policies beyond 2014.

Practical implications – Relevance of testing performance in evaluating product quality in order to reduce food fraud.

Originality/value – This research paper identifies and indicates how European Union regulations influence the increase of quality testing performance and the need to develop reference materials used in agri-food engineering.

Key words: EU policies; food safety; quality management

1. Introduction

This paper assesses the impact of European Commission (EC) policies on increasing testing performance and developing RMs, specific, to food engineering. In this view, the authors carried out a documentary study on the dynamics of the EC policy in the field of RM production and the implementation of these policies beyond 2014. The year 2014 was chosen as a landmark because the policies in the field of food safety have expanded their regulatory area by including provisions regarding food fraud. Thus, the European Parliament recommends to the EC and Member States to stimulate research programs to develop technologies for food fraud detection. The EC proposes a financial support for the strategy developed by the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) and for the justified initiatives to increase the quality of agri-food products. EU Member States

transpose the EC regulations and finance at national level projects to increase the testing performance of agri-food products.

Renée Johnson, agricultural policy specialist at the Congressional Research Service (CRS), noted in the report "Food Fraud and Economically Motivated Adulteration" about the economic consequences of food frauds and substantiated the need for food fraud to be included into food safety policy (Elliott, 2013).

On the other hand, Elliott's report on "Integrity and assurance of food supply networks" elaborated for United Kingdom Government, supports the periodic review of the methodologies used. Recommendation 4 (Laboratory Services) mentions that those involved in the food chain audit and inspection should have access to sustainable laboratory services and the Government should facilitate the standardization of the methods used by the laboratories (C. Elliott, 2014), the need for new RMs being closely linked to the development of these new analytical methods.

European Parliament also called on the EC legislation review in this area, in order to reduce the risk of food fraud. Legislative proposals were also requested in accordance with Regulation (EU) no. 1151/2012 regarding quality schemes for agri-food products. In the same context, the European Parliament recommends to the EC and the Member States to stimulate research programs to develop the technologies and methods used to detect food fraud.

Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy in Germany, in partnership with National Physical Laboratory (NPL) in UK and Laboratoire National d'Essais in France coordinate the international database named COMAR, Code d'Indexation des Matériaux de Référence, developed in 1970 by Laboratoire National d'Essais (LNE) and approved by the ISO Committee for Reference Materials (ISO-REMCO) (COMAR, 2017).

2. Materials and Methods

The authors of the paper conducted a documentary study in order to present the decisive role of the European Commission's policy in developing the RMs specific to food engineering. It involved a documentary study consisting in EU regulations and reports, research strategies and projects, national legislation and scientific articles, as well as international standards. The instruments for the implementation of EC policies at EU level in the field of testing of agri-food products have been also identified.

Both the increase of the quality of life and the smooth functioning of international trade depend on reliable measurements, which eliminates the errors of testing results and the need for re-testing of food that are coming with additional costs. Certified reference materials (CRMs) are used for the reliability of the measurements.

Certified reference material (CRM) is a reference material for which it can be found the traceability of specified characteristics in a certificate (International Organization for Standardization (ISO), 2007).

2.1. EU regulations

The quality of agri-food products is a priority at European level, so by issuing regulations targeting the food sector, the European Union draws guidelines regarding quality management for testing and monitoring these products.

On the agenda of the European Council, the existing legislative package on animal and plant health focusses on modernizing and simplifying the existing rules, while strengthening compliance with health and safety standards throughout the agri-food chain. The package is consisting in five legislative proposals submitted by the Commission, the fourth proposal foreseeing the creation of a single framework for all official control actions along the agri-food chain. The negotiations between the European Parliament and the Council on the proposal for a regulation on animal health were completed in June 2015, and the regulation was adopted on March 9 and published on March 31, 2016 (European Council, n.d.). It will be applied from April 21, 2021.

In the last two decades, the European Union has carried out an intense activity for developing the specific tools for implementing food safety, including the mitigation against food fraud. From 2000 until now, the

European Union has issued regulations in this field, one of the first being Regulation 178/2002, the regulation establishing the general principles and requirements of the food law, establishing the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) and establishing procedures in the field of food safety (European Parliament, 2002).

2.2. Research Infrastructures

The Joint Research Center (JRC) is the European Commission's internal scientific service, with the mission to provide scientific support and identify key issues in the agri-food field. In order to achieve its objectives, JRC has laboratories and facilities for the development and production of RMs at international level. JRC Institute of Reference Materials and Measurements (IRMM) in Geel, Belgium has pilot plants for the processing of unique multi-parameter reference materials.

In the context where bio-terrorism is a risk factor for food safety, class 3 bio-safety laboratories are under construction within the JRC to provide the European Commission internal access to laboratory facilities where human pathogens (bacteria and viruses) can be used to develop new CRMs (European Commission, n.d.-a).

JRC develops MRs according to the requirements generated by the European policies in the field of food safety, in particular, supporting the emerging fields, such as nanotechnology, biotechnology and personalized medicine. Moreover, in 2018 JRC provided through public calls, access to the nanobiotechnology pilot station (Braskem, 2017), and support in the development of RMs (Joint Research Center, n.d.).

Taking into consideration the importance of the quality of the results obtained from food testing, for risk assessment/management in the field of laboratory analysis, the European Commission, has selected at EU level, EU reference laboratories (EURL) that support the activities of the European Commission in implementing food safety policies.

EURLs are responsible for providing national reference laboratories (LNR) with analytical methods and diagnostic techniques, RMs and testing schemes for laboratory competencies, to train LNR staff, but also to provide the European Commission with scientific and technical expertise, in terms of laboratory analysis. The activity of EURL groups ensures better implementation of EU legislation, for example, by assessing legislative limits and reducing the need for repeat testing which it means time and money consuming. As a result, the functioning of the EU internal market is strengthened and consumers benefit from safer foods on the market. Information on the competence of the EURL can be found on the European Commission's website (European Commission, n.d.-d).

2.3. Research projects

Knowing the importance of food testing in monitoring food safety and the not sufficient existing testing methodologies, Giovana Zappa (Zappa & Zoani, 2015) proposed in 2015 to include the project "Infrastructure for promoting metrology in food and nutrition" with the acronym METROFOOD in the Roadmap agenda prepared by ESFRI, a project funded by the European Commission, in 2017. An important objective of the project is the realization of the scientific research infrastructure necessary to evaluate the quality of food products and, thus, to provide adequate tools for identifying the food frauds (Zoani, 2016).

METROFOOD is coordinated by the National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development (ENEA) and currently involves 48 European research organizations and one international (FAO) from 18 European countries (MetroFood, 2020).

2.4. International standards

Quality management, as defined by international standards, is the administration of all functions and activities necessary to determine and achieve quality. At the same time, it is a part of total management, including the definition, organization and implementation of quality policy in order to ensure and control the quality of all processes, products or services. (Sitnikov, 2014)

An important role in the standardization of the food field was played by the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), established in 1945 by the Organization of the United Nations. Under FAO coordination, following the Codex Alimentarius Austriacus a model, Codex Alimentarius (Codex) and

the first collection of international product standards, was developed. Although not mandatory, Codex standards are a source of information on technical specifications, composition and quality parameters, labeling, and methods of analysis and sampling.

Standardization of the specific requirements is necessary in establishing the degree of conformity of the product. The International Organization for Standardization (ISO) plays the decisive role in the development and promotion of international standards. It carries out an intense activity in standardizing the quality requirements of the products and the analytical methods, afterwards the standardization has extended to other important elements in increasing the confidence in the quality of the products: among them, the labeling is intensely regulated in the context in which it was found that the label is the vector to the consumer of all the food legislation.

The international (ISO/IEC) and European (CEN/CENELEC) standardization bodies, through the elaborated standards, provide technical support for performing procedures used in mutual recognition of the results of conformity testing with the standards.

2.5. Financing tools

The main objective of Regulation (EU) no. 652/2014 (for expenditure on the food chain, for the health of animals and plants) (European Commission, 2014) is to contribute to ensuring a high level of health for humans, animals and plants. Costs related to food fraud for the global food industry have been estimated at around € 30 billion each year, posing a real threat to the proper functioning of the Common Market 18 (European Commission, n.d.-b).

3. Results and discussions

The legislative requirements in the field of food safety and the testing of the quality of agri-food products increase the demand for specific products and services. Thus, the test laboratories accredited according to ISO 17025 are required to prove their competence by declaring the degree of measurement uncertainty performed on RMs and through inter-laboratory tests.

In this context, the Elliott Report (C. T. Elliott, 2014) prepared for the Government of the United Kingdom emphasizes that some adulterants are undetectable by existing techniques and, therefore, a special role lies in the scientific research in identifying new markers, analysis techniques and periodically reviewing the methodologies used, the need RM being closely linked to the development of these new methods of analysis.

For RMs producers, the information regarding the regulation of food quality represents opportunities to diversify RMs producing that support the implementation of the new regulations. Thus, the EC regulation regarding the declaration of the country of origin of the main ingredient (raw material) generates the elaboration of test standards regarding and the need for RMs.

The European Union regulations with impact on the activity of the RMs are presented in table 1.

Table 1. EC regulations governing food safety (selection) Subsection

Regulation number	Description
Regulation 1829/2003	on genetically modified food and feed
Regulation 853/2004	on food hygiene
Regulation 2073/2005	on microbiological criteria for foodstuffs
Regulation 1881/2006	establishing the maximum levels for certain contaminants in food products
Regulation 2158/ 2017	establishing mitigation measures and reference levels for reducing the presence of acrylamide in foodstuffs
Regulation 1169/2011	on informing consumers about food products

The European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures plays an essential role in the development of policies on research infrastructure in Europe.

Through its policies, the European Commission supports research to increase the quality of food testing results applicable within the EC. In this context, the EC has been supporting the development/production of RMs for more than four decades, with the establishment of the European Community Reference Office (BCR) in 1980. Joint Research Center is one of the world's leading developers and producers of RMs. Currently it offers over 760 RMs and distributes around 20,000 units per year to laboratories worldwide. The certified RMs produced and distributed by the JRC provide the measurement laboratories with means to validate the analytical methods and to evaluate the accuracy of their measurement results. The JRC also develops RMs based on the requirements generated by European food safety policies, especially in emerging fields, such as nanotechnology, biotechnology and personalized medicine. To achieve its objectives, JRC has laboratories and processing facilities for the development and production of unique RMs in the world.

Regarding the RMs for food matrices in Romania, there is no RM/ CRM producer, the only option for national laboratories being the purchase of CRMs from external producers.

The implementation of the METROFOOD project will generate knowledge in two closely related areas, metrology and food quality. The implementation stages of the METROFOOD project are presented in table 2 (European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures, 2018).

Table 2. METROFOOD project execution stages

Phase	Period	Objective	Financing
PRO-METROFOOD	2016-2017	Preparation of the project for inclusion in ESFRI	Horizon 2020 No 739568
METROFOOD-RI	2015-2017	Design and feasibility phase	H2020 INFRADEV-02-2019, CSA
METROFOOD-PP (GA 871083)	2018-2021	Creation of pan-European research infrastructures ESFRI	ESFRI
	2021-2024	Project implementation	

Following the completion of the FoodIntegrity project, FERA represents the United Kingdom in key European and international regulatory committees (e.g. EFSA, CEN, CODEX and ILSI) and is a national reference laboratory designated for a number of food contaminants and residues in food (Food Integrity, 2020).

European Program for the establishment of validated procedures for the detection and identification of biological toxins, EuroBioTox, is a project funded by the EC with the budget of 7,998,747 euros through the program "Fight crime, illegal trafficking and terrorism, including understanding and tackling terrorist ideas and beliefs (H2020-EU.3.7.1.)". The project is being implemented during 5 years, 2017-2022, and the 14 partners in 7 countries (Germany, France, Belgium, Switzerland, Finland, Great Britain and Sweden) are developing microbiological methods for determining pathogens in food products used as crime vectors (*Project "EuroBioTox,"* n.d.).

Official controls from Member States are an essential tool for verifying and monitoring the implementation and compliance with the relevant requirements of the European Union. The effectiveness and efficiency of the official control systems are vital to maintaining a high level of safety for humans, animals and plants along the food chain, while ensuring a high level of environmental protection. Financial support from the European Union should be available for such control measures. In particular, a financial contribution should be made to the Union reference laboratories to help them to cover the costs resulting from the implementation of work programs approved by the Commission, in accordance with Appendix 20 of Regulation (EU) NO. 652/2014 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 May 2014 and Appendix 22 of the same Regulation specifying that the EU should allocate funds for the technical, scientific, coordination and communication activities that are necessary to ensure the correct implementation of EU law and to ensure the adaptation of the right to scientific, technological and societal developments (European Commission, 2014).

The general budget of the European Commission for the period 2014-2020 is € 1,891,936 million and is intended to finance food safety programs. From table 6 it can be seen that the budgetary allocation has had an upward trend, the value of the investment in the field of food security increasing steadily from year to year.

Table 3. General budget of the European Commission for the period 2014-2020

Year	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	TOTAL 2014-2020
Mi. Euros	253.39	258.53	264.07	270.23	276.69	282.69	286.33	1.891.936

For the implementation of food safety policies EC has allocated EUR 1.68 billion for the financial cycle for the period 2021-2027 (European Commission, n.d.-c).

As a result of the implementation of EC policies at the international level, there is an increase in the number of laboratories accredited in accordance with the ISO 17025 standard (figure 1).

Figure 1. The total number of laboratories accredited in accordance with ISO 17025

Also, according to the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), there is an increase in the production of RMs. 10,000 RMs are registered in COMAR database, which reflects the interest of laboratories in developing them (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Number of RMs registered in COMAR database (situation in 2019)

As noted, 17% of the RMs registered in COMAR database are produced in Japan, followed by Germany with a percentage of 13% (Figure 3).

Figure 3. % RMS registered in the COMAR data base

Conclusions

As a priority for the European Union, food safety is intensely regulated and monitored. Through its policies, the European Commission addresses food safety in an integrated way, by offering both specific regulations and the appropriate tools for their implementation at European level. In this context, there is an intensive activity of harmonizing the instruments for assessing the quality of foodstuffs in the EU member states, increasing the analytical performance and developing new food matrices used as CRMs. The RMs have a wide applicability in the testing activity regulated by the international standard ISO 17025, but also in the quality evaluation of the results obtained from the analytical tests, the calibration of the analysis equipment, the validation of the methods and the estimation of the measurement uncertainty.

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